

POSSIBILITIES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECOTURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Ecotourism may be regarded as a management tool that aims to reconcile both conservation and development goals. The article aims to develop proposals and recommendations on ways to organize and develop ecotourism in Uzbekistan. Also, during the reform of the tourism sector, activities aimed at improving the organization of ecotourism activities and its market, determining its place in general tourism, ensuring the competitiveness of national tourist products in the international tourism market and increasing the export of tourism products learning according to the requirements, the development of scientific and practical directions in improving the management of ecotourism activities also serves this purpose.

Key words: ecotourism, tourism, cultural and historical potential, international travel destinations, increase in the number of tourists, tourist products, the state committee of the republic of uzbekistan on the development of tourism, tourism information centers.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the best ways of having rest. Tourism is a travel branch that can have recreation, religion, health, business purposes. It has become very popular since XIX and technological progress. Tourism starts to be a part of the people's life in global world. Developing tourism sector increases the number of travelers every year. The countries with rich nature, architecture, culture, history are more likely to attract many tourists. Azerbaijan is lucky among countries that it has many features for the development of tourism sector.[1] Tourism has a huge impact on the development of countries' economies as a complex. Increasing economic activities are supported by tourism service sector. Many such reasons make tourism sounds very attractive for the solutions of socio-economic problems. The development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan not only opportunities to solve the problems of spirituality, science, culture, enlightenment, nature protection, to increase the interest of ecotourists in our mother nature, to preserve and continuously enrich the unique flora and fauna, but also to improve the living standards of the local population, economic issues , providing them with jobs, expanding the possibilities of making a significant contribution to the preservation of our world-famous ancient cities and historical monuments that attract foreign travelers, the prosperity of our country, and the prosperity of our compatriots. Tourism is considered one of the best ways of non oil sector and the development of service sector will benefit the economy of the country. The goal of ecotourism is the rational use of nature in the tourist direction to ensure ecological safety and sustainable development of current and future generations. Therefore, in the economic development of our country, it is very important to determine the role and importance of ecotourism in the economy, analyze the parameters of development, apply it to the tourism of our republic, organize the market of ecotourism activities and develop its promising directions.[2] There are many urgent

problems in the industry that are waiting for a solution. The necessity of their in-depth study, conclusions obtained through scientific analysis, and suggestions for generalization of the knowledge gathered in the field shows the relevance of the research topic.

RELATED WORK

According to Indian researchers, Joyshree Nath and Asoke Nath, Environmental impacts on ecosystems are described as following:

Whenever the negative impacts on the natural environment are dealt with, it should be considered that these impacts rarely affect only one entity. The impacts on the natural environment do not only affect untouched nature areas, but also cultivated lands. Agricultural lands are an important part of the natural and cultural heritage of a region and ecologically valuable because it's the habitat of many species. Environmental impacts of tourism occur at the local, regional and global level. Climate change and the depletion of the ozone layer are the two major impacts on environment. Environmental impacts primarily affect the local and regional level and at the same time they affect the environment globally in the long run. Basically, the loss of biological diversity is a major consequence of these impacts.[3]

PROPOSED IDEA

In economically difficult times, the population is the only material resource relies on natural economy, and therefore cattle breeding and rapidly develops agriculture. Naturally, in such conditions, plow and pasture parks and nature reserves under state protection are also used for this purpose. As a result, there is an active "attack" of people on the territories that have not yet been mastered. as a result, the ecology will be destroyed and some species will disappear. Uzbekistan According to Article 3 of the Law of the Republic "On Forests", the forest massifs are mainly ecological (water conservation, protection, sanitary-hygiene, health, recreational), aesthetic and others whose use is restricted performs tasks.[4] Development of tourism and the government should be the leading reformer in revitalizing recreational activities. Because the careless and unplanned use of nature is great for the country can cause damage. Therefore, in our republic, this field is special there is an approach and important decisions are being made. For example, Uzbekistan "Natural resources comprehensive and consistent plan for conservation and development of the Chimyon-Chorvok area It is noted in the decision No. 83 on the provision of access the region is a resort and recreational character due to its natural and climatic conditions belongs to a specially protected natural area. In this regard, to nature environmental threat caused by enterprises that cause significant damage in order to reduce and determine the potential of local tourism infrastructure restructuring was carried out in the area. Negative to nature any industry, agriculture and other enterprises that have an impact construction was prohibited. Currently, ecotourism products are among foreign and domestic tourists the need is great. According to experts, Central Asia is in the bosom of nature may become a special "Mecca" for tourists. That's it 17 of 2006 of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in April "Service and service of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2006-2010 PQ-325- in order to implement the decision and develop ecotourism State Committee for Nature Protection "Environmental in the Republic of Uzbekistan the concept of tourism development and its prospects in the near future" developed.

The development of the local association should be supported by the state and society. This issue is particularly related to land use, taxation, licensing and registration of economic

activities, border issues. Ecotourism based on current legislation Several views of development can be offered: - creation of a center for the development and support of ecological tourism (creating laws on the tourism of specially protected natural areas, destinations, ecotourism regions, etc.); - creation of ecological tourism infrastructure (free tourist areas, tourist laws on guaranteeing foreign investments involved in the construction of objects, supporting private entrepreneurship in tourism create etc.). Great opportunities for the development of ecological tourism in Uzbekistan there is. Attractive mountains and rivers, beautiful scenic landscapes, traditional lifestyle, historical and religious centers are the most necessary factors for ecological tourism. The development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan should become an integral part of the strategy of sustainable tourism development in the republic. It is worth noting that adventure destinations are not very attractive for ecotourists at the moment. Therefore, the main attention should be paid to the form of tourism that allows you to enjoy natural beauty. Regarding the improvement of transport services and border areas activities can be offered: 1. Pick-up and transportation services. Reception and transport services for tourists arriving by public transport can be organized in Tashkent and Ghazalkent for Chimyon-Bildirsoy, Khumson, Aktash and Burchmulla-Nanay regions. Transportation services are provided by local association groups or private taxi drivers. 2. Crossing the border. In order to solve the problems related to the border crossing of tourists visiting the Western Tien Shan region, it is very important to do the following: Continue the work related to the agreement on the establishment of the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and It is necessary to carry out activities that will allow the development of cross-border tourism among Kyrgyzstan, that is, to restore old points for crossing the border or to open new ones. 3. Crossing restricted areas. Movement of tourists It is necessary to agree on the procedure with law and order and security authorities, to define the limits of the places where they can be and prohibited areas. In close cooperation with interested tourist companies and local individuals, define routes and types and develop a movement scheme, taking into account the interesting places in the area (cultural objects, nature, landscape) must Several routes have been identified so far in close cooperation with local association groups.

CONCLUSION

By way of a conclusion, the main goal of the development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan is to meet the needs of society, to introduce a market economy model at the level of world standards into the sector with the expansion of the quality and scope of service. is to provide. Satisfying the needs of society, the demand of tourists for internal and external tourism services, and the needs of the population for excursion services. with the study of international demand for import and export of services shows how important the issue is. Based on these, the results obtained during the research of the role and importance of ecotourism in the tourism service market of Uzbekistan gives the following conclusions. 1. Ecotourism is an important part of traditional tourism, and it is a new perspective direction in terms of its formation. Currently it is a general tourist occupied 10-20 percent of the market, and the growth rate is increasing year by year is going 2. Despite the great potential of ecotourism in Uzbekistan, the level of its use is quite low. The country's wealth of natural landscapes, unique flora and fauna, rare, internationally important archaeological finds, paleontological remains, geological sections and natural monuments is evidence of the potential for rapid development of ecotourism. 3. Ecotourism is not only a source of income, a

means of providing employment, a factor of recreation that gives people pleasure and aesthetic satisfaction, but also one of the ways to preserve, maintain and improve the environment. should also be considered as 4. In most cases, terms such as "natural tourism", "sustainable tourism", "green tourism", "responsible tourism", "charity tourism" are used as an alternative to ecotourism. Although there is a commonality between them, they cannot be synonymous with each other. But all of them mean a trip to nature, nature conservation and, on this basis, the goal of protecting the environment.

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